

Establishment of baseline data of the indoor air quality of offices in Metro Manila

M. Zali (1), M.C. Belino (2), H.F.R. Bosshard (3), E.G. Dela Cruz (4)

1. mood_i91@yahoo.com

2. mcbelino@mapua.edu.ph

3. hfrbosshard@gmail.com

4. efren.delacruz@dlsu.edu.ph

(1), (2), (3) School of M.E. and MfgE, Mapua Institute of Technology

(4) M.E. Department, De La Salle University – Manila

Abstract

The study is a commissioned research by the Philippine Society of Ventilating, Air-Conditioning and Refrigeration Engineers (PSVARE) Foundation, Inc. to establish baseline data regarding the indoor air quality and thermal comfort of offices in Metro Manila. The study involves measurement of space temperature, space relative humidity and air velocity and determination of the concentration level of gaseous contaminants, biological contaminants and particulate matter. The gaseous contaminants conducted in the study include carbon dioxide, carbon monoxide, sulphur dioxide, ozone, formaldehyde, radon, lead, and total volatile organic compounds. The biological contaminants include airborne bacteria and fungi, while particulate matter includes PM10 and PM2.5. This paper presents the preliminary results and, therefore, a work-in-progress.

Keywords

Indoor Air Quality, thermal comfort, gaseous contaminants, biological contaminants, particulate matter

1 Introduction

Indoor air quality (IAQ) is a discussion about the state of ambient air quality inside buildings and its effects on resident's health and performance. The indoor air pollutant can be two to five times bigger than outdoor level (U.K EPA 2013). These have various reasons, including poor building's design, heating and cooling system and inappropriate ventilation that cause indoor air pollutant and can have detrimental effects on the health of occupants. The sources of indoor air pollutants are mold and pollen, tobacco smoke, chemical products, gases such as radon, carbon monoxide and carbon dioxide, etc.

A study in 1987 showed that indoor air pollution is one of the cancer risks, out of 13 environmental problems (U.S. EPA 1987). According to the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), radon is the second-leading cause of lung cancer and rated as the number one environmental health risk. Poor indoor air quality inside a building can cause heart disease, headaches, loss of eyesight, eye, nose and throat irritation, asthma, etc.

Carbon dioxide is a good indicator of indoor air quality because it can distinguish the condition of ventilation system and other important factors. If the amount of carbon dioxide reaches higher than the standard it can affect the occupant's health. Previous studies showed that there is a relationship between IAQ and worker's performance. For example, if an employee stays in a room with uncomfortable temperature he/she will lose his/her concentration or vice-versa, if he/she works in a hot office he/she will get thirsty and keeps sweating, and he/she will lose a lot of time which cause poor performance and productivity loss. Therefore, IAQ standard is required in offices for better result of employee's performance.

This study is a segment of a baseline data preliminary study of the Philippines Society for Ventilating, Air-conditioning and Refrigerating Engineers (PSVARE), and it will use CO₂ concentration level for determining indoor air quality. It considered an office space in a building in Makati City. The main parameter that was measured and monitored is carbon dioxide concentration level, which is a good indicator for indoor air quality. In addition, the temperature and relative humidity of the indoor space were also monitored.

2 Methodology

The office considered in this study is located in Makati City. This office is an engineering design company with more than 20 employees and it has an area of 120 m², and divided

into five different zones for measurement of indoor air quality, and another zone outside of the office. Figures 2.1 and 2.2 show the 3-D floor plans of the office under consideration. Area 1 is a conference room which is located at the right side of the entrance door and separated from the hallway by a partition door. The number of occupants in this area is between 1 to 5, but most of the time is vacant. Area 2 is the administration room which is located in front of the conference room with three employees working in the area and had two doors, one facing the collider, and the other one facing the designing area. The designing area was divided into 2 (areas 3 and 4) where the engineers are working with their computers. The majority of the employees are working in these sections. The pantry (area 5) is where the employees make coffee and wash their dishes. The comfort rooms are inside the pantry area. It should be noted that the pantry has no ventilation system and most of the time the water boiler is working. The last area (area 6) which is located outside of the office was selected for calculating the ventilation rate and comparing the indoor and outdoor air quality of the office. The measurement device for gathering data of outdoor parameters was placed in emergency balcony.

An ocular inspection was done by the team to become more familiar with the building and at the same time, to determine the sampling points. The ocular inspection was done during the first hour of the sampling day on May 4, 2015. Survey questionnaires were distributed to the employees present in the building to know their complaints with regard to the indoor air quality in the office.

Figure 2.1 – 3-D floor plan drawing

Figure 2.2 – 3-D floor plan drawing

The sampling of air was done from May 4 to May 8, 2015. The parameters measured were CO₂ concentration level, temperature and relative humidity, which were recorded every 20 minutes from 8:00 AM until 5:00 PM. TSI 7525 was used for indoor air quality measurements (Figure 2.3). This device can measure CO, CO₂, humidity, temperature, dew point and wet bulb simultaneously.

Figure 2.3 – TSI 7525 IAQ measurement device

3 Results and discussion

The following discussions include the results of the survey, analysis of data, and correlation.

3.1 Results of survey

The survey questionnaires were distributed to 16 out of 19 office occupants (4 female and 12 male) on the second floor of the building. The average working experience of the employees in this office was 8 years, and they spent 33 hours per week in the office. Sixty percent (60%) of the respondents had ages from 20 to 29 years old. Sixty three percent (63%) of them were former or current smokers. Almost all the respondents worked with computers, wherein the average usage was 7 hours a day. The survey report cited that more than twenty percent (20%) of occupants complained about indoor air quality in their workplace. Majority of the occupants reported sensitivity to tobacco odor and other chemicals in the office. Most of the employees reported complaints involving headache, dizziness, light headedness and numbness in hands after leaving the office. Other complaints include noisy environment, dusty place, temperature too cold, and cough.

3.2 Analysis of data

The results of the samplings done during the five consecutive days would reveal that the measured maximum CO₂ concentration levels in the office exceeded the 1000 ppm limit set by ASHRAE. Similarly, the average CO₂ concentration levels measured during the five consecutive days either closely approached or exceeded the 1000 ppm limit. In both cases, the CO₂ concentration levels (maximum and average value) were very much below the 5000 ppm limit set by DOLE-OSH. These can be visualized in Figure 3.1.

The maximum temperature levels in some points exceeded the 23-28 °C limit set by ASHRAE for summer (light clothing) but, the average of temperature in these five consecutive days did not exceed the ASHRAE standards as shown in Figure 3.2. However, from the result of survey done, about 25% of employees were not satisfied with the temperature level and they felt cold at work.

The relative humidity obtained ranged from 40.5% to 45.3% which did not exceed the ASHRAE standard limit of 30-60%, as shown in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.1 – Average CO₂ concentration level during 5-day sampling

Figure 3.2 – Average temperature in C during the 5-day sampling

Figure 3.3 – Average relative humidity in percentage during the 5-day sampling

3.3 Correlation

Based on the correlation results, there was a very weak relationship between CO₂ concentration level with temperature and relative humidity. There was also a weak relationship between CO₂ concentration level and number of people, because all the calculated values were $-0.5 < x < 0.5$.

4 Conclusion

The average values of the relative humidity obtained in the office space ranged from 40.5% to 45.3% which were within the ASHRAE recommended design room relative humidity range of 30% to 60%. The temperature obtained in the office space ranged from 24.8 C to 27.4 C, which was within the ASHRAE recommended design room temperature range of 23 C to 27.8 C for summer (light clothing). Despite the relatively much higher temperature in some areas, twenty five percent (25%) of the occupants complained that the room temperature was too cold for them. Thus, the thermal comfort level based on ASHRAE recommended values was not suited for them. The average values of the carbon dioxide concentration level obtained either approached closely or were beyond the ASHRAE indoor air quality standards limit of 1000 ppm. On the other hand, based on the Philippines DOLE OSHC standard limit of 5000 ppm, the average values of the carbon dioxide concentration level were far below. Thus, the office space had good indoor air quality if DOLE-OSHC standard was used and poor indoor air quality if ASHRAE standard was used.

The study will continue to consider IAQ of other buildings as part of the establishment of baseline data of indoor air quality of offices in Metro Manila. The future study will include gaseous and biological contaminants as well as the particulate matter.

5 References

1. U.S. EPA. (2003). A Standardized EPA. Protocol for Characterizing Indoor Air Quality in Large Office Buildings.
2. U.S. EPA. (1987). Ambient Monitoring Guidelines for Prevention of significant Deterioration.

3. Wolkoff, P. (2012). Indoor Air Pollutants in Office Environments: Assessment of Comfort, Health, and Performance. *International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health*.
4. ASHRAE. (2010). Ventilation for Acceptable Indoor Air quality. ASHRAE Standard.
5. DOLE-OSHC. (1989). Occupational Safety and Health Standards. Manila.
6. L.E. Burton, B. B. (2000). Baseline Information on 100 Randomly Selected Office Buildings in the United States (Base): Gross Building Characteristics. *Proceeding of Healthy Buildings*, 1.
7. L.T. Wong, K. M. (2008). An Energy Impact Assessment of Indoor Air Quality Acceptance for Air-Conditioned Offices. *Energy Conversion and Management*.
8. Philomena M. Bluysen, S. J. (2011). Assessment of Wellbeing in an Indoor Office Environment. *Building and Environment*.
9. Sayareh, G. (2010). Assessment and Improvement of the Indoor Environmental Quality of Cummins Technical Service Center.
10. Scientific Committee on Health and Environmental Risks (SCHER). (2007). Opinion on risk assessment on indoor air quality.
11. Skön, R. J. (2004). Modeling Indoor Air Carbon Dioxide (CO₂).